

Fusion of cellulose microspheres with pulp fibers: Creating an unconventional type of paper

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ABSTRACT

Cellulose microspheres (CMS) are a type of spherical regenerated cellulose particles with versatile properties which have been used as carrier materials in medical and technical applications. The integration of CMS into paper products opens up novel application scenarios for paper products in a wide range of fields. However, the incorporation of CMS carriers into paper products is challenging and hitherto no reports do exist in literature. Here, we present a feasibility study to incorporate up to 50 w.% CMS in paper hand sheets using retention aids. Our primary observations highlight the successful formation of uniform paper hand sheets retaining its tensile strengths at elevated CMS concentrations. Sheets with high CMS contents exhibit an increase in density and display enhanced surface smoothness — an outcome of a CMS layer forming atop the fiber base — which effectively bridges voids and rectifies surface irregularities as supported by Gurley testing, infinite focus microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. While our primary objective centered on the general feasibility to manufacture CMS-containing papers, the resulting composite scaffold carries significant potential as a platform for innovative, functional paper-based materials.

1. Introduction

Biobased microspheres as functional carriers for manifold applications have seen tremendous increase in popularity in the past 25 years. The main advantage is that these microspheres can be easily equipped with functional groups on their surface or by entrapment of functional materials in their matrix. It is not surprising that microspheres from many materials including starch (Pereira et al., 2013), protein-chitosan blends (Müller et al., 2011), gelatin-fish collagen composites (Kozłowska et al., 2018), and cellulose have been intensely researched in this context. Cellulose microspheres (CMS) represent a unique form of regenerated cellulose known for their spherical morphology, and narrow particle size (Gericke et al., 2013). They feature a porous structure, large surface area, hydrophilicity, chemical reactivity, potential for functionalization, and considerable mechanical strength (Thümmler et al., 2010). These promising characteristics enable a broad spectrum of applications spanning drug delivery (Choy et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2010; Maiti et al., 2009; Volkert et al., 2009), enzyme immobilization (Luo & Zhang, 2010b), chromatography (Luo & Zhang, 2010a; Weber et al.,

2010), tissue engineering (Liu et al., 2010) and water remediation (Borchers & Pieler, 2010; Carvalho et al., 2021). CMS can be loaded with drugs and tailored to release them at a specific rate (Maiti et al., 2009) as well as to target them to specific locations (Luo et al., 2009). A drug delivery system for bone regeneration was developed by encapsulating Ceftriaxone, an antibacterial agent, in CMS. These drug-loaded microspheres were then integrated into a scaffold composed of hydroxyapatite/polyurethane for bone tissue engineering applications. The incorporation of the drug-loaded CMS within this matrix offered a sustained release of the antibiotic, enhancing its effectiveness in combating infections and supporting tissue regeneration (Liu et al., 2010). Beyond medicine, CMS find applications in chromatography for separation and purification processes (Luo & Zhang, 2010a). Commercially available cellulose-based microspheres like Cytopore™ with a mean diameter of 230 μm are already employed in suspension culture systems and can facilitate cell growth (Cytiva, 2023).

In general, CMS fabrication follows a three-step approach: (i) the dissolution of a cellulosic material either by direct or derivatizing solvents (ii) the transformation of the resulting solution into spherical

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particles, and (iii) the solidification of these particles. Dropping and dispersion are the two most common techniques to shape the dissolved cellulose into spheres. Dropping methods, where a cellulose solution is dropped into a coagulation medium generate larger beads (0.5–2 mm). Dispersion, on the other hand, involves high-speed mixing of a cellulose solution with an immiscible solvent (Kulterer et al., 2012; Wagenknecht et al., 1996). This creates emulsions that can be stabilized with surfactants, resulting in much smaller droplets (100 nm to μm range) compared to dropping techniques (Gericke et al., 2013). For example, cellulose acetate (CA) beads can be used as precursors for CMS by dissolution of CA in a water immiscible solvent (e.g. ethyl acetate). Upon combining the CA solution, with an aqueous phase containing a tenside, protective colloids and salts, cellulose acetate droplets form, which are then subsequently separated, washed and converted to cellulose (Thümmeler et al., 2010).

Pulp fibers could potentially serve as a matrix for the incorporation of microspheres. In papermaking, spherical particles such as inorganic fillers like CaCO_3 are frequently used because they improve brightness, opacity, smoothness, dimensional stability, and print quality. As fillers are introduced prior to paper structure formation, they significantly impact paper properties beyond simply occupying void spaces. Optical properties and permeability can be influenced as the proportion and dimensions of empty spaces within the paper matrix substantially affect these characteristics. Substituting some of the fiber mass with smaller particulate material often results in a smoother product. Moreover, fillers can influence the resulting thickness and diminish the paper's strength properties by interrupting fiber bonding. Adding 10 % of filler by mass typically leads to a 20 to 25 % reduction in paper strength, although notable variations exist. Generally, the fiber debonding effect of fillers increases with decreasing particle size because of higher surface area, impeding direct contact between adjacent fibers and reducing the elastic modulus. Fillers tend to attach to small fibrils protruding from fiber surfaces (Hubbe & Gill, 2016). In industrial papermaking, retention of inorganic fillers is insufficient because of the large mechanical forces during dewatering. It is improved using retention agents, which create interactions between fillers and fibers. Inorganic fillers can also interact directly with fibers through physical mechanisms such as friction and entanglement (Chen et al., 2011). However, these interactions are weak compared to physico-chemical bonding.

There has been substantial research focused on developing organic–inorganic composites capable of establishing strong binding with cellulosic fibers. Among the most promising composites are combinations of conventional fillers and renewable carbohydrate materials like starch and wood fines. These materials exhibit the capacity to create strong hydrogen bonds with the surrounding fiber matrix. Nelson and Deng (2007) focused in their research on the improvement of bondability between inorganic particles and polysaccharide substrates through encapsulation with regenerated cellulose. Unlike unmodified inorganic fillers, the free glucose hydroxyls of regenerated cellulose participate in hydrogen bonding with cellulose molecules on the fiber surface. This supplementation of hydrogen bonds in the bonded fiber area contributes to increased bonding efficiency. Their studies indicate that the encapsulated fillers form bonds with fibers on the order of starch–fiber and fiber–fiber bonds (Nelson & Deng, 2007).

Regenerated cellulose surfaces, like those of CMS, lack external fibrils, which are a significant factor in the strength of fiber–fiber bonds through mechanical interlocking. In addition to mechanical interlocking, the bonding between fibers is governed by other mechanisms such as interdiffusion, induced dipoles, coulomb forces, and hydrogen bonds (Weber et al., 2014). Torgnysdotter and Wagberg (2003) determined the joint strength of regenerated cellulose fibers. Their findings suggest that the surface charges of fibers play a crucial role in the development of both joint strength and paper strength (Torgnysdotter & Wagberg, 2003). In a more recent study, Weber et al. (2014) investigated the relative bonded area (RBA) of hand sheets made from viscose fibers. The RBA was calculated using the Page equation and measured by

the light scattering method. To use the Page equation, the breaking length of hand sheets, the bond strength of fiber joints and the optical bonded area of fiber–fiber joints were determined. The authors discovered that adding organic additives like carboxy-methylcellulose and cationic starch, especially when both are added, leads to an increase in breaking length and RBA. However, the specific bond strength of the tested viscose fibers was ten times lower than that of pulp fibers. This can be attributed to the rather amorphous nature of viscose fibers, a consequence of the dissolution and regeneration process used in their production, coupled with the absence of a mechanical interlocking mechanism (Weber et al., 2014). Thus, the question remains whether it is possible to form stable hand sheets with a high amount of regenerated cellulose spheres to be used as a potential carrier of substances to replace some portion of the pulp fibers. Mechanical interlocking of CMS and fibers is unlikely, but as Nelson and Deng (2007) suggested, there is a possibility of hydrogen bonding between particles having a regenerated cellulose surface and pulp fibers.

Organic microspheres, such as CMS, present an opportunity to introduce advanced functionalities into paper. These particles can act as carriers for a variety of substances, opening up possibilities for innovative applications of paper in both technical and medical contexts. However, to the best of our knowledge, the combination of cellulosic fibers with CMS as functional carriers for manufacturing of papers has not yet been described in scientific literature as basic question on their manufacturing have been remaining elusive so far. It is unclear whether a large number of CMS can be retained during the sheet forming process and whether it is possible to even produce mechanically stable paper with high CMS content. In papermaking, filler loading using inorganic pigments is conventionally expressed in weight percentage. However, because of the low density of CMS particles compared to conventionally applied inorganic fillers, achieving comparable loadings with CMS presents a challenge, as a significantly higher number of particles has to be incorporated in the paper network in case of CMS. Therefore, the objective of this study is to validate the feasibility of incorporating CMS into laboratory hand sheets and to assess their impact on paper properties. Specifically, we aim to evaluate the conditions under which conditions CMS containing paper sheets can be successfully manufactured.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Commercial unbeaten bleached hardwood pulp from Lenzing (Lenzing, Austria) was used to prepare the hand sheets. The main components of the pulp fibers are 94.56 % cellulose and 5.48 % hemicellulose, with 0.41 % ethanol-toluene extractives and a low lignin content of 0.01 %. The cellulose content was determined according to Kürschner and Hoffer (1931), while the lignin content was assessed using the Klason lignin method (T 222 om-02). Moreover, the pulp has a water retention value of 64.6 g/g, a zeta potential of -20.5 mV and a length weighted average fiber length of 0.722 mm.

2.1.1. CMS preparation

The CMS were fabricated following the procedure described in Thümmeler et al. (2010). In this procedure, a mixture is prepared by combining dissolved methyl cellulose and sodium acetate trihydrate. Subsequently, a tenside dispersion in ethyl acetate is added, followed by the addition of dissolved cellulose acetate. To achieve a homogenous emulsion, the mixture is dispersed at 13,500 rpm. Afterwards, solvents are removed by a rotary evaporator, yielding cellulose acetate beads. These beads are then subjected to a purification process involving multiple cycles of centrifugation and resuspension in water. To convert the cellulose acetate beads into the desired cellulose microspheres, a deacetylation step is applied. This involves stirring the beads in ethanol, followed by the addition of dissolved sodium hydroxide. After a period

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the hand sheet forming process. Created with BioRender.com.

Table 1

CMS content and dry mass of fabricated hand sheets. The letter in the sample description represents the CMS content (B = blank (target 0 w.%), L = low (target 10 w.%), H = high (target 50 w.%)) and the number represents the total hand sheet grammage.

Sample description	CMS content [w.%]	Dry hand sheet mass [g]
B80	0.00 ± 0.00	2.41 ± 0.02
L80	9.89 ± 0.41	2.40 ± 0.01
H80	51.21 ± 1.42	2.46 ± 0.07
B160	0.00 ± 0.00	4.76 ± 0.03
L160	9.45 ± 0.32	4.77 ± 0.02
H160	48.53 ± 0.40	4.66 ± 0.04

of stirring and resting, the mixture is centrifuged and resuspended in water. Finally, acetic acid is used to neutralize the suspension. The resulting cellulose microspheres have a diameter of 1.5 μm (d_{50} , particle size distribution is presented in the Supporting Information), a porosity of 68 %, and a specific surface area of 5 m^2/g . Cationic polyacrylamide (Percol 830-AP, BASF, Ludwigshafen, DE) was used as a retention agent (RA).

2.2. Production of hand sheets with CMS

Fig. 1 illustrates the applied hand sheet production method using the Rapid-Köthen sheet former (FRANK-PTI) according to ISO 5269-2. First, a defined volume of fiber suspension was added to a beaker and stirred using a magnetic stirrer. Using a high precision scale, the desired mass of CMS suspension was added to the beaker. After one minute of stirring, a weighted solution containing 0.1 w.% of the RA was added. The added RA mass remained constant at 1.2 % by weight relative to the amount of added CMS. The resulting mixture was then transferred to the Rapid-Köthen sheet former. Following the dewatering step, the pulp was covered with the two standard cover paper sheets and placed into the drying unit. After 10 min of drying the cover sheets were peeled off. Ten hand sheets per sample with a grammage of either 80 g/m^2 or 160 g/m^2

were produced. Afterwards, the paper samples were stored in a climatized room at a temperature of 23 °C and 50 % humidity according to ISO 187.

To achieve the desired CMS contents of 10 w.% and 50 w.%, a surplus of CMS suspension was added based on the CMS retention. In this study, the CMS retention indicates the weight percentage of CMS remaining in the paper after sheet forming using a Rapid-Köthen sheet former. For instance, if the CMS retention was 65 %, the CMS mass used for the fabrication of the hand sheets was determined by dividing the desired CMS mass by 0.65. Table 1 summarizes the hand sheets fabricated by this procedure.

2.3. Determination of CMS retention

To determine the retention of the CMS, a subset of hand sheets from each trial point was placed in a drying oven for 10 min, and their dry mass was measured. Using the dry mass of the hand sheets, along with the dry fiber and CMS mass, the retention can be calculated using eq. (1).

$$\text{Retention} = \frac{\text{hand sheet mass} - \text{fiber mass}}{\text{added CMS mass}} \quad (1)$$

Since the loss of the unbeaten pulp fibers in Rapid-Köthen sheet forming is approximately 1 %, it was not factored into the calculation of the CMS retention and content (see Supporting Information).

2.4. Hand sheet characterization

2.4.1. Micro-roughness (infinite focus microscopy (IFM))

The surface of the paper samples was analyzed using focus variation microscopy with an InfiniteFocus microscope from Alicona (model ALC13) with a vertical resolution of 600 nm. For the analysis, three 3 × 3 mm images per side of each sample were taken at a magnification of 20×. The micro-roughness (roughness <100 μm) of the samples was calculated using Measure Suite 5.3.5 software (Alicona, Austria). The Sdr value was selected to represent the differences in roughness. It quantifies the deviation of the calculated surface roughness in percent

Fig. 2. Visualization of the comparative analysis performed in the results chapter.

from an ideal smooth surface.

2.4.2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the paper samples were obtained using a TESCAN VEGA3 (TESCAN, Czech Republic) at an acceleration voltage of 10 kV and detected with a secondary electron detector. The electron source was a tungsten cathode. Prior to imaging, the paper samples were coated with gold using a sputter-coater (Cresington 108 auto sputter coater) for 60 s.

2.4.3. Optical microscopy of cross-sections

Cross-sections of each paper type, with a thickness of one micrometer were obtained using an automated microtome. The paper samples were embedded in a HEMA (2-Hydroxyethylmethacrylate)-based resin (Technovit® 7100, Sanova Pharma GesmbH), sliced and imaged using a fully automated rotary microtome (RM2255, Leica) according to [Wilt-sche et al. \(2011\)](#).

2.4.4. Thickness

The thicknesses of the paper samples were determined according to ISO 534 using a L&W micrometer (type 222) with a resolution of 1 μm . The mean value for each sample type was determined from 50 individual measurements (5 measuring points per paper sample, 10 samples per type).

2.4.5. Air permeability

The air permeability of the paper samples was determined using the Gurley method with a L&W densometer (Type 969,478), as specified in ISO 5636-5. To obtain a mean value for each type, 50 individual measurements were performed (5 measuring points per paper sample, 10 samples per type).

2.4.6. Tensile test

The strength properties of the papers were determined using a horizontal tensile tester (FRANK-PTI) in accordance with ISO 1924-2. Two

Fig. 3. Grammage (a), composition (b) and CMS retention (c) of the different hand sheet sample types.

Fig. 4. SEM images of the wire sides of 80 g/m² samples at low magnification: 10 w.% CMS (a) and 50 w.% CMS (b), and at high magnification: 10 w.% CMS (c) and (d).

strips with a width of 15 mm were cut out from five samples of each type to obtain a mean value from 10 individual measurements.

3. Results and discussion

Diagrams depicted in this chapter display mean values of the determined hand sheet properties. The corresponding standard deviations are indicated either as an error bar in the bar charts or as a colored shade in the effect plots. All mechanical tests were performed in a climatized room at a temperature of 23 °C and 50 % humidity according to ISO 187. Fig. 2 illustrates the types of hand sheets that are compared with each other and the information that can be obtained. These comparisons are performed to explore the impact of CMS incorporation on the hand sheet properties. The analysis is conducted from two distinct angles: a traditional approach (part 1) and a more unconventional viewpoint (part 2). This allows for the determination of whether the observed properties of the sheets are a result of the inherent characteristics of CMS or stem from the reduced fiber mass of the hand sheets with CMS.

3.1. Composition of paper samples and retention of CMS

Six different types of paper samples were produced (see Table 1), each featuring varying CMS contents (blank = 0 w.%, low = 10 w.%, and high = 50 w.%) and possessing a grammage of either 80 or 160 g/m². Pretests of paper samples weighing 80 g/m² without RA addition revealed that the mean CMS retention of samples with 10 w.% CMS was low at about 30 %. Under the same conditions, samples with 50 w.% CMS exhibited an even lower mean retention of only 12 %. Fig. 3, c

illustrates that the addition of 1.2 w.% RA significantly improved the retention of CMS. Samples with 80 g/m² and 10 w.% (L80) exhibited a retention of 59 %, while samples with 80 g/m² and 50 w.% (H80) CMS exhibited a retention of 68 %, which is more than a fivefold increase compared to samples of this type without RA. With RA, the higher CMS amount of H80 compared to L80 likely leads to the formation of larger agglomerations that can be better retained in the fiber matrix. Another factor influencing the retention is the fiber mass. As Fig. 1 illustrates, the CMS are introduced into an aqueous suspension of pulp fibers before being fed into the Rapid Köthen sheet former. By doubling the mass of fibers and CMS, a thicker filter cake is formed on the wire in the column during dewatering. This increased fiber mat thickness on the wire provides more opportunities for the smaller CMS to be effectively trapped and retained during sheet formation. As a result, the retention of CMS increases with increasing fiber mass per sample (Fig. 3, c).

3.2. Microscopy

3.2.1. SEM

At low CMS content (Fig. 4, a), the CMS primarily cluster around the contact points between fibers and fill small inter-fiber voids. Given their shape and size, CMS particles show accumulation patterns similar to that of calcium carbonate fillers. They fill voids between fibers, distribute themselves across the surface, and may even become partially embedded within the walls of pulp fibers (Chen et al., 2011). The marking within Fig. 4, c highlights the formation of a bridge-like structure by the CMS connecting two fibers. Fig. 4, d depicts an area exhibiting high fibrillation and CMS concentration. This finding demonstrates the positive impact of external fibrillation in forming a tightly woven network of

Fig. 5. Effect plots of fiber mass per sample (a) and CMS content (b) on the surface (micro-roughness). IFM images of top sides of samples containing 10 w.% (c) and 50 w.% (d) CMS.

fibers and CMS. The presence of fibrils creates additional binding sites for the CMS, while the RA promotes CMS adherence through electrostatic interactions. As the CMS content is increased to 50 w.% (Fig. 4, b),

certain portions of the fiber surfaces become entirely covered by CMS. This phenomenon, observed in highly inorganic filler loaded papers like preceramic paper (Travitzky et al., 2008), is expected to be even more

Fig. 6. Optical microscopy images of hand sheet cross-sections with grammages of 80 g/m² (a, b, c) and 160 g/m² (d, e, f), respectively. The images depict samples with 0 w.% (a) and (d), 10 w.% (b) and (e), and 50 w.% CMS (c) and (f). Note that the SEM images in the upper row (a-c) have a different magnification than the lower row (d-f).

Fig. 7. Effect plots of fiber mass per sample (a), (c), (e) and CMS content (b), (d), (f) on the hand sheet thickness, apparent density, and the normalized air volume flow through the sheets. To ensure that the volume flow is comparable between samples of different grammage, the sheet thickness was normalized to 100 μm .

pronounced for CMS due to their lower density. The CMS layer on top of the fibers minimizes or eliminates fiber interstices completely.

3.2.2. IFM Micro-roughness

An increase in CMS content results in a significant reduction of surface roughness and effectively eliminates the differences between the wire and top sides of the paper (Fig. 5, b). The higher roughness of the top side stems from the sheet forming process. At lower amounts of 10 w.% CMS, the CMS tend to accumulate on the wire side during Rapid Köthen column dewatering, resulting in less CMS on the top side and, therefore, in higher surface roughness. At high amounts of 50 w.% CMS, more CMS are already retained on the top side of the paper hand sheets during Rapid Köthen dewatering. Thus, at 50 w.% CMS content, the difference in surface roughness between both sides of the sheet disappears. Therefore, the irregularities caused by the fibers are easily compensated by the high amount of CMS. The surface roughness of the highly loaded samples (50 w.% CMS) with 2.4 g fibers is higher than that of the samples with 1.2 g fibers (Fig. 5, a). This indicates that the

accumulation patterns of the CMS vary depending on the fiber mass. A higher amount of CMS probably accumulates in the bulk of H160 samples, while more CMS adhere to the surfaces of B80. Since the fiber filter cake in the column during the dewatering step of the sheet formation is thicker for H160, there are more binding sites within, thereby reducing the amount of CMS on the surface. A property that these carrier particles share with conventional fillers is their smoothing effect, which can be attributed to the void closure between the fibers (Gill, 1995). A comparison between the IFM images of the top sides of the blank (Fig. 5, c) and the high-loaded paper (Fig. 5, d) confirms a more uniform surface with increased CMS content.

3.2.3. Optical microscopy of cross sections

The optical microscopy images of the paper cross-sections (Fig. 6) confirm the trend of decreasing surface roughness with increasing CMS content. This is observed for samples of both grammages (80 g/m^2 : a, b, c and 160 g/m^2 : d, e, f). At 50 w.% CMS, the fibers are embedded in a dense CMS matrix. Smaller inter-fiber voids are filled with CMS, while

Fig. 8. Effect plots of fiber mass per sample (a), (c) and CMS content (b), (d) on the tensile index and elongation at break of the hand sheets.

large voids remain, as can be seen in Fig. 6, f. Overall, the samples with 50 w.% CMS seem to have the highest density. When the CMS content is lower, the CMS adhere to the fiber surfaces, resulting in a reduction of the void volume between fibers. However, their number is insufficient to efficiently close voids. The microscopy images further illustrate a decrease in thickness with increasing CMS content.

3.3. Comparative analysis part 1

The analysis of the subsequent section is conducted according to the methodology outlined in Fig. 2, part 1. In this context, hand sheets containing CMS are compared with blanks of equivalent grammage, i.e. of higher fiber mass. This comparison enables the investigation of the impact of fiber substitution with CMS.

3.3.1. Bulk properties

As the dimensions of fibers significantly exceed those of CMS, the thickness increases with higher fiber mass. On the other hand, substituting fibers with CMS results in a thinner paper. This effect is known in papermaking when high filler quantities are used (Hubbe & Gill, 2016). It is even more pronounced for CMS carrier particles, as these share similar sizes with inorganic fillers but are higher in number at identical loading levels when expressed as weight percent due to their lower density. An increase in fiber mass has a negligible effect on the apparent density. However, CMS, because of their size and tendency to occupy small inter-fiber voids, increase the apparent density when their added amount is increased.

An increase in fiber mass reduces permeability only when the paper does not contain CMS. However, when CMS are added, the increased fiber mass no longer affects the air volume flow through the paper. Instead, the CMS densify the paper. This becomes apparent in Fig. 7, f where the high and low grammage samples with equal CMS content exhibit nearly similar air volume flows. The decline in permeability is

more pronounced between 0 w.% and 10 w.% CMS, leveling off between 10 w.% and 50 w.% CMS. This is probably related to different CMS accumulation patterns at low and high CMS contents. CMS predominantly adhere to specific sites, such as small voids between fibers. The closure of these voids leads to the sharp decrease in permeability. Certain larger voids cannot be closed, even at 50 w.% CMS. Therefore, the permeability decline is lower between 10 w.% and 50 w.% CMS.

3.3.2. Tensile strength properties

The increase in the tensile index of the blank samples correlates with higher fiber mass, which leads to a higher number of fiber-fiber bonds and consequently enhances tensile strength. However, when substituting a portion of fibers with CMS, this effect diminishes as the number of fiber-fiber bonds decreases. Although some interaction may occur between CMS and fibers, it can be assumed to be weaker than direct fiber-fiber bonds, causing a substantial decrease in the tensile index with increasing CMS content. This finding aligns with the research by Weber et al. (2010), who demonstrated that viscose fibers, which also consist of regenerated cellulose, exhibit a significantly lower bonding efficiency compared to pulp fibers. Interestingly, this trend was not that evident between blanks and 10 % CMS samples of low grammage (Fig. 8, b). The replacement of 10 % of fibers with CMS did not significantly impact the tensile index of paper samples weighing 80 g/m². However, for those weighing 160 g/m², this substitution led to a decline in strength compared to the blank. This discrepancy remains unclear and needs further investigation. CMS restrict fiber mobility, thereby diminishing the paper's capacity to stretch and deform prior to breaking. This phenomenon becomes apparent as the elongation at break decreases at higher CMS contents. The elongation at break is higher for paper samples with a grammage of 160 g/m² because the increased fiber mass results in more fiber bonds, enabling higher elongation before breakage.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the thickness (a), moisture content (b), normalized air volume flow (c) and apparent density (d) of three samples: one consisting solely of 2.4 g fiber (B80), another consisting of 2.4 g fibers and 2.4 g CMS (H160), and the third consisting of 4.8 g fibers (B160).

Fig. 10. Comparison of the tensile strength (a) and elongation at break (b) of three samples: one consisting solely of 2.4 g fiber (B80), another consisting of 2.4 g fibers and 2.4 g CMS (H160), and the third consisting of 4.8 g fibers (B160).

3.4. Comparative analysis part 2

The analysis in the following section employs the methodology described in Fig. 2, part 2. Hand sheets containing CMS are compared with blanks of lower grammage, i.e. of equivalent fiber mass. The consistent fiber mass shared between the blanks and the CMS-containing hand sheets facilitates an evaluation of how the intrinsic characteristics of CMS affect the paper's properties.

3.4.1. Bulk properties

The increased thickness of H160 compared to B80 suggests that the CMS not only fill small inter-fiber voids but also cause the fibers to

spread apart. This could be a consequence of the retention agent, which causes the CMS to agglomerate and form bigger particles. CMS consist of an amorphous regenerated cellulose structure, which has a greater tendency to absorb water than the semi-crystalline fibers (Nelson & Deng, 2007). As a result, the moisture content of H160 is higher than that of B80 and B160. The bulky nature of fibers prevents them from densely packing during sheet formation, while adding the smaller sized CMS results in void filling and therefore in a lower air permeability as well as in an increased density of the sheets (Fig. 9, c and d).

3.4.2. Tensile strength properties

Fig. 10 a demonstrates that H160 has a higher tensile strength than

B80, indicating that the added CMS do not impair bonding between fibers. Agglomerates of CMS adhere to fiber surfaces, fill voids, and bridge small fiber interstices, thereby providing additional stability to the paper. However, this interaction is apparently weaker than a fiber-fiber bond, as the tensile strength of B160 is above that of H160. Regenerated cellulose surfaces, such as those found on CMS and viscose fibers, tend to create weaker bonds compared to pulp fibers. This is because they lack external fibrils, which play a crucial role in providing a mechanical interlocking mechanism (Weber et al., 2014). The smaller size of CMS in comparison to fibers results in a reduced contact area, which consequently contributes to their lower bonding efficiency. Furthermore, the CMS restrict fiber movement during the tensile test, resulting in H160 exhibiting a lower elongation at break compared to B80 and B160.

4. Conclusions

We could demonstrate that the incorporation of CMS into paper is possible, particularly when utilizing retention aids and higher fiber masses to produce sheets. This, as well as the superior strength properties suggest that producing CMS papers of higher grammages is favorable. The SEM images confirmed that CMS preferably adhere to fibrils protruding from the fiber surface. Thus, further research should focus on refining the pulp before sheet formation. Highly loaded hand sheets exhibit a smoother surface compared to blanks, as a CMS layer forms on top of the fibers, eliminating voids and other irregularities. The void-filling effect of the CMS was further validated by SEM and the reduced air permeability.

Fiber-fiber bonded area was identified as the primary determinant of hand sheet strength. This is due to the stronger bonds formed between fibers compared to those between CMS and fibers, facilitated by the larger size of the fibers and the presence of mechanical interlocking mechanisms. Hand sheets containing 50 w.% of CMS have fewer fiber-fiber bonds than those of the same grammage consisting only of fibers. If CMS interfered with fiber bonding, the strength of the high-loaded sample (H160) would have been below that of the blank with the equivalent fiber mass (B80). In fact, H160 is even slightly stronger than B80. Whether a CMS containing paper is mechanically weaker than paper without CMS depends on the type of blank it is compared to. When compared to a blank with the same grammage (i.e., higher fiber mass), it shows weaker mechanical performance. However, when compared to a blank with lower grammage but same fiber mass, it is equally strong or even slightly stronger.

The use of paper-based matrices for embedding cellulose microspheres (CMS) brings multiple advantages. Firstly, the paper serves as a matrix that offers mechanical support to the CMS, enhancing their potential shelf life by protecting them from environmental exposure and contamination. Additionally, when formed as a paper sheet, CMS can be conveniently utilized to cover many types of surfaces. The paper also functions as a secondary barrier, allowing for the controlled release of substances from within the CMS. This attribute is particularly advantageous in applications such as controlled flavor release in food packaging, or for the gradual dispensation of pharmaceuticals in transdermal drug delivery systems. Consequently, this integration facilitates innovations in medical treatments, where transdermal patches embedded with CMS can deliver therapeutics at precisely regulated rates, unlike the application of individual microsphere particles.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexa Scheer: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Johanna Fischer:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Adelheid Bakhshi:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Wolfgang Bauer:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Steffen Fischer:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Stefan Spirk:** Writing – review &

editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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